

Climate disinformation on Google Search

Åsa Rolfsdotter Söderberg^a and Agnes Tibbelin^b

^a University of Borås, Allégatan 1, 503 32 Borås, Sweden

^b University of Borås, Allégatan 1, 503 32 Borås, Sweden

Purpose and research questions

This poster presents a bachelor thesis study about climate disinformation on Google Search in relation to Google's principles of Expertise, Experience, Authority and Trustworthiness (EEAT) and the concept of Your Money or Your Life (YMYL). The study aims to contribute to the knowledge about greenwashing on the search engine Google search. Greenwashing is a form of climate disinformation where companies present exaggerated or false climate claims (Greenpeace, 2025). The following research questions are addressed: “Does Google Search contribute to making greenwashing visible, and if so, how?” and “How can the search results be understood in relation to Google's principles of trustworthiness?”.

Background

The year 2024 had the highest temperatures ever recorded, which highlights the escalating urgency of the climate crisis (Copernicus, 2025). Scientists stress the need for immediate and large scale measures, particularly transitioning from fossil fuels to renewable energy (IPCC, 2023). At the same time, climate disinformation continues to spread (Calvo, Iranzo-Cabrera & Tarullo, 2024; Bakowicz, 2024). Not only does climate disinformation damage source trust (Sundin, 2024), it also complicates and delays climate action (Ekberg, Forchtner, Hultman, & Jylhä, 2023). Greenwashing is a form of climate disinformation, where marketing portrays polluting industries as environmentally responsible (Greenpeace, 2025). This can mislead consumers, undermine informed decision making, ultimately harming both individuals, democratic society and the environment (Williams, 2024; Tandoc, Lim, & Ling, 2017). Users trust in Google Search to provide reliable and accurate information (Lewandowski & Schultheiß, 2022), which Google Search claims to do through the principles of trustworthiness, *EEAT*. Websites concerning money or health, which by Google are labelled *YMYL* are according to the company, moderated more carefully (Google, 2025). However, Google Search faces criticism for not taking sufficient measures to limit the spread of climate disinformation (Haggin, 2021). After this criticism, Google Search claims to incorporate zero tolerance for climate disinformation on the platform (Greenpeace, 2025; Kundaliya, 2021). In this study this claim is reviewed.

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EMAIL: asa.rolfsdotter.soderberg@gmail.com (A. 1); agnestibb@gmail.com (A. 2)

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Method and theory

This thesis is based on an algorithmic audit, i.e. a structured review of the ranking that orders the search results on Google Search. The study investigates the search terms *climate neutral* and *net zero emissions* as well as a sample of companies publicly accused of greenwashing in Sweden. The study uses RAT (Result Assessment Tool) for data collection (Sünkler et al, 2024), and a content analysis with a coding scheme (Bryman, Clark, Foster, & Sloan, 2025) to detect greenwashing. Frame theory is used to analyse visible and invisible meaning and perspectives (Entman, 1993), that are shown in the first twenty results in the SERP (Search Engine Results Page).

Results, analysis and conclusion

The result suggests that Google contributes to making greenwashing visible on Google Search. This is in line with the report *Greenwashing on Google* (Ahmed, 2021) from the organisation CCDH (Center for Countering Digital Hate) but in this case in a Swedish context. However, more studies are needed to form a firm conclusion. As previous research discusses, the climate crisis can be framed as a public health issue (Ebi, et al., 2021). It could therefore be argued that websites with climate claims that affect people's economy or health ought to be moderated as YMYL and according to the principles of EEAT.

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